

SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATIONS OF CHLORINE, NITROGEN AND ARSENIC IN ORGANO- ARSENIC COMPOUNDS.

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The present work was undertaken with a view to find out a suitable method for the simultaneous and rapid determinations of arsenic, nitrogen, and chlorine, the latter being attached to arsenic. Of these three elements the chlorine linked to arsenic deserves special attention. The extreme ease and rapidity with which this element undergoes changes renders its determination difficult by most of the existing methods. In order to shorten time several processes, outlined by different investigators, were tried but without any satisfactory results. Robertson's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 902) gave unsatisfactory results on account of very rapid evolution of hydrogen chloride which could not be trapped in the absorption tubes. Similarly Nomura and Murais' method (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1924, 38, 217) presented the same difficulties as in Robertson's process. By applying ter Meulen's method (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1928, 47, 698) it was observed that the catalyst was coated with a deposit of metallic arsenic and that the reactions in many cases were not complete and even with the same substance varying results were obtained which were gradually on the decrease. If, however, asbestos fibres be placed on either sides of the catalyst, the results obtained are more or less comparable.

The process is based on the fact that organic compounds, containing the above mentioned elements, are decomposed when treated with a mixture of potassium sulphate, sulphuric acid and a little metallic selenium as a catalyst, with the liberation of hydrogen chloride and selenium chloride which are quantitatively absorbed in alkaline hydrogen peroxide. The absorbed chloride may be estimated either volumetrically or gravimetrically. In the latter case, however, the associated selenium should be first precipitated by sodium bisulphite. Arsenic and nitrogen are retained by the sulphuric acid mixture. The nitrogen in the digestion flask is liberated as ammonia and is estimated by the usual method. The arsenic left is first of all reduced to trivalent state by sodium bisulphite and then titrated iodimetrically after separating the precipitated metallic selenium. The digestion period is only from 25-35 minutes but the duration depends solely on the nature of the substances to be treated and in

cases of volatile compounds, this should be increased so as to avoid loss by volatilisation of the original compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The Apparatus.—A flask of 250 c.c. capacity was used for effecting the digestion of the compound. It was fitted with a ground-glass joint to which was attached a stoppered funnel (10 c.c.), the stem reaching nearly to the bottom and ending in capillary and the exit-tube contained a trap at the middle. The absorption apparatus consisted of a simple modification of the well-known Peligot bulb-tube and a second smaller tube which served as a guard. This was connected to a water-jet pump.

FIG. 1.

Reagents required are pure sulphuric acid, pure potassium sulphate, 15% sodium hydroxide solution, hydrogen peroxide free from chloride, and pure metallic selenium. It is advisable to carry out a blank experiment with the reagents mentioned to ensure that the materials are free from chloride, arsenic and nitrogen under exactly the same conditions as in actual estimation.

Procedure.—The substance (0.1–0.2 g.) was accurately weighed out into the digestion flask and 7.8 g. of pure potassium sulphate and 5–10 mg.

of metallic selenium were introduced into the flask. The ground-glass joint, lubricated with syrupy phosphoric acid, was fixed into position and the flask was connected with the system of absorption tubes. The first absorption tube contained 15 c.c. of 15% sodium hydroxide solution, containing an equal volume of hydrogen peroxide, and the second tube contained 10 c.c. of alkali solution with the same volume of the peroxide. The funnel was filled with 10 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid and the pump started, when the sulphuric acid came down. The flask was allowed to remain for 15 minutes with occasional shaking and then heated slowly over a small flame. The contents of the flask at first became dark, which gradually turned colourless or light yellow after passing through intermediate shades of colour. During the whole operation a stream of air should be maintained and its rate increased towards the end. The acid mixture should boil during the last stage and the boiling should be prolonged for 5 minutes more after complete digestion. The different elements were then estimated as described below.

Estimation of Chlorine.—The contents of the absorption tubes were washed into a beaker and the chlorine estimated either gravimetrically or volumetrically. In the former case the solution was boiled to expel the hydrogen peroxide, treated with 1 c.c. of a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite solution and after 2-3 minutes gradually acidified with nitric acid. The solution was then filtered from precipitated selenium and the excess of silver nitrate solution added. The precipitated silver chloride was filtered into a weighed Gooch crucible, washed, dried and weighed in the usual manner. In the latter case, the solution was boiled, acidified with nitric acid and 10 c.c. (or more) of *N/10*-silver nitrate solution added, filtered from the precipitated chlorides and the excess of silver titrated back with *N/10*-ammonium thiocyanate solution in the usual manner.

Estimation of Nitrogen.—The ammonia present in the digestion flask was expelled with strong solution of sodium hydroxide and was estimated as in the method of Kjeldahl.

Estimation of Arsenic.—The contents of the digestion flask after removal of ammonia were washed into a bigger vessel and 10 c.c. of a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite added and then acidified slowly by sulphuric acid. The solution was boiled to expel all the sulphur dioxide, cooled and filtered from the precipitated selenium. The filtrate was neutralised by excess of sodium bicarbonate and the arsenic was titrated by *N/20*-iodine solution. (1 c.c. of *N/20*-iodine = 0.001875 g. of arsenic).

The following table shows the nature of the results obtained in the cases of substances examined by this method :

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Compound.	Chlorine		Arsenic		Nitrogen	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Methyldichloro-A	43.89 %	44.09 %	46.3 %	46.5 %		
Ethyldichloro-A	40.6	40.5	42.6	42.8		
β -Chlorovinyl-dichloro-A	51.08	51.31	36.2	36.1		
$\beta\beta'$ -Dichloro-divinylchloro-A	45.8	45.6	32.1	32.1		
$\beta\beta\beta''$ -Trichloro-trivinyl-A	40.75	41.4	28.8	28.9		
$\beta\beta'$ -Dichloro-divinylmethyl-A	33.5	33.31	35.4	35.2		
Phenyldichloro-A	31.6	31.8	33.5	33.6		
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl-arsonic acid	—	—	30.4	30.3	5.5	5.6
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl-arsonic acid	—	—	30.1	30.3	5.48	5.6
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl-arsonic acid	—	—	30.2	30.3	5.45	5.6

(A stands for arsine)

This method is not applicable, however, to the estimations of bromine and iodine in the corresponding organo-arsenic halides.

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